

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior: Mediation Role of Creative Self Efficacy and Creative Process Engagement

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Abstract

This research further investigates the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and innovative work behavior using the mediating role of creative self-efficacy and creative process engagement (study of food and beverage business actors in Malang). This research uses food and beverage SMEs in Malang as research objects. Determining the sample size for this study used a purposive sampling technique with a sample of 150 respondents. The data collection method uses a questionnaire; the data is analyzed using PLS-SEM. The research results show that entrepreneurial leadership, creative self-efficacy, and creative process engagement influence innovative work behavior. Additionally, creative self-efficacy and creative process engagement can mediate the influence between entrepreneurial leadership and innovative work behavior.

1. Introduction

Innovation as an important factor has a significant role in maintaining an organization's competitive advantage, especially in business-oriented organizations; innovation is necessary to become a market winner so that it can continue to survive and develop (Shanker et al., 2017). Janssen (2000) calls this behavior innovative work behavior (IWB), which involves creating, introducing, and implementing new ideas deliberately designed in a job, group, or organization to gain benefits from better performance. Several factors can stimulate innovative work behavior in business people. However, leaders, compared to other factors such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and

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work motivation, have a more significant influence in maintaining the sustainability of organizations/businesses and encouraging individuals to display IWB (Li & Soulivanh, 2019).

Leadership influences and guides others (individuals or groups) to understand and agree on achieving specific goals (Yukl, 2009). Specifically, entrepreneurial leadership as a leadership skill in creating creativity is one of the critical factors in increasing an individual's IWB (Mawarni & Fasa, 2021). *Entrepreneurial leadership* has been defined as a type of leadership behavior that enables leaders to face the increasing challenges of their tasks and roles in today's organizational environment (M. . Gupta, 2004)

The empirical study of (Bagheri et al., 2020) and (Newman et al., 2018) proves that entrepreneurial leadership positively and significantly influences a person's tendency to display IWB at work (V. Gupta et al., 2017) explained that innovative performance results are separate from the role of inspiring leaders. Based on the differences in research results, this research is an alternative to bridging the inconsistencies in the findings of previous studies through the role of creative self-efficacy and creative process engagement as mediating variables in the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and IWB.

Creative self-efficacy was chosen as the first mediating variable based on several considerations. First, previous research has investigated and proven that entrepreneurial leadership is vital in creating creative self-efficacy. Leaders can play various roles depending on the work situation, such as recognizing good ideas, identifying critical organizational problems, influencing work goals, and providing technical and rational stimulation (V. Gupta et al., 2017). Second, creative self-efficacy can influence IWB. As a form of self-confidence in producing creativity, creative self-efficacy strongly correlates with an individual's high tendency to behave innovatively in the workplace (Akbari et al., 2021; Hsu et al., 2011) (2021) and Teng et al. (2020) show that creative self-efficacy convincingly influences a person's IWB.

Furthermore, creative process engagement in this research is also a mediating variable for the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on IWB. Theoretical and empirical foundations are used to make creative process engagement a mediator of the relationship between these two variables. First, creative process engagement, as a person's dedication to a job, is an essential concept for organizations, and leadership plays a significant role in the creative engagement process (Sahu et al., 2018). Creative process engagement refers to the process in which creativity occurs. Second, creative process engagement, as individual involvement in processes relevant to creativity, is a necessary first step toward innovation (Saeed et al., 2019). Bakker and recent empirical studies show that creative process engagement strongly influences IWB (Afrin et al., 2022).

Based on the explanation above, creative self-efficacy and creative process engagement are essential variables in realizing IWB. Because of these various theoretical and empirical foundations, researchers place creative self-efficacy and creative process engagement as mediating variables and alternatives in bridging several inconsistent previous study findings regarding the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and IWB, as previously explained.

Covid-19, which occurred in Indonesia, changed socio-economic conditions and the business environment in Indonesia. Implementing the Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) policy influenced one of these changes. Implementing social distancing, limited transportation, and the closure of crowded centers to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 virus have limited people's movement and activities. This condition ultimately creates a less conducive situation for business and impacts business actors. Micro and Small Enterprises (UMK) are one of the business groups affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. In 2020, as many as 2.78 million MSE businesses stated that the pandemic

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affected their business (BPS, 2022). This impact occurs in all industrial groups with quite varying percentage sizes.

The impact of the pandemic felt by IMK businesses is quite varied. However, the most significant impact was a decrease in demand or sales of goods/services (54.09 percent), an increase in raw material prices (15.76 percent), and delays in buyers' payments (14.32 percent). One of the reasons for the decline in sales of goods/services is changes in people's behavior during the pandemic. Situations that often change due to the implementation of various policies make people more selective in sorting out expenses. Apart from that, the impacts felt were scarcity of raw materials (9.79 percent), reduced number of workers (3.61 percent), and others (2.43 percent).

If we look at the business sector in MSEs, based on BPS data released on March 4, 2022, most Indonesian micro-small scale businesses or industries (UMK) operate in the food sector. The number of MSEs in the food sector reached 1.51 million business units in 2020. The proportion of MSEs in the food sector reached 36% of all national IMK, which totaled 4.21 million business units. Meanwhile, the proportion of MSEs in the beverage sector was 93.2 thousand.

Based on these data, this research will only focus on micro and small businesses (UMK) operating in the food and beverage/culinary sector in Malang City. This is also based on several considerations. First, Malang is an educational city with dozens of universities; this is an opportunity for the continued growth of various food and beverage-based businesses with promising market share. Second, the culinary business is a type of business that is easy to observe, imitate, and modify. Considering that this business tends to be easy to imitate, this requires business people to continue to innovate. Third, the city of Malang has renewed consumers. Malang City is an education city; every year, there are approximately 200 thousand immigrants, most of whom are students from outside the city of Malang, whose characteristics vary, including an interest in types of food and drinks. Therefore, customer-oriented innovation is essential to carry out.

Apart from data on the impact of Covid-19 on MSEs at a macro level, as mentioned above, researchers obtained specific data from the MSE group in Malang City, namely 29 micro and small businesses of four types, including food, drinks, frozen food, and cakes & snacks. During the pandemic, the sales turnover of business people experienced a very significant decline due to the large-scale social restriction policy by the government, which had an impact on the business side of business people in the city of Malang. There was a decrease in monthly sales turnover of 29 micro businesses in Malang City even some businesses, such as Bluederhood Malang, Warung Sedap, Tahu Susu, Pempek Mang Johan, etc., experienced a decline of more than 50% during the pandemic. Apart from the pandemic and large-scale social restrictions, problems such as the lack of creativity and innovative workforce behavior are also determining factors for the decline in turnover.

Innovation, which comes from innovative work behavior, still needs to be solved by MSEs in Malang City. Hanifawati & Suryantini, (2015) confirmed this condition where there are still many SMEs that do not have an awareness of sure standardization, weak product innovation capabilities, and a lack of skilled and creative labor so that the quality of the products produced is often inconsistent and difficult to develop. As has been explained, innovative work behavior (IWB) is one of the principal non-financial capital for organizations/businesses to survive and achieve competitive advantage (Örnek & Ayas, 2015). Therefore, building IWB among business people is necessary so businesses can develop, not stagnate or experience decline. As explained above, factors such as entrepreneurial leadership, creative self-efficacy, and creative process engagement have been proven to play a crucial role in shaping a person's IWB, especially in the business sector. Creative self-efficacy and creative process engagement in this research were tested as variables that have a direct influence and as mediators of the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on IWB.

2. Research Hypothesis

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on IWB

Employee innovative performance results are not related to the role of inspiring leaders and role models (V. Gupta et al., 2017; Nazir, 2014), through their study on leadership and innovative work behavior, revealed similar results, namely that leadership style tends to negatively influence employees who show IWB. Another study by (Bagheri et al., 2020; Newman et al., 2018), in structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis revealed that entrepreneurial leadership plays a significant and positive role in employee IWB. From the description above, the first hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1: Entrepreneurial leadership positively and significantly influences Entrepreneurial Leadership on Creative Self-Efficacy

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Creative Self-Efficacy

Entrepreneurial leadership characterized by Framing the challenge, Absorbing uncertainty, Path-clearing, Building commitment, and Specifying limits can significantly and positively encourage employee self-confidence in generating creative ideas (Mehmood et al., 2020). This has also been confirmed by (Fatoki, 2021; Sarwoko, 2020), who found a positive and significant correlation between entrepreneurial leaders and employees' creative self-efficacy. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and significant effect on creative self-efficacy

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Creative Process Engagement

Engaging employees in a particular job is one of the significant challenges for organizations. When employees involve themselves in cognitive processes relevant to creativity, this is called creative process engagement (Saeed et al., 2019). Several previous studies also support the results of this research; for example, (M. T. et al., 2019; Yulivan, 2021) revealed that entrepreneurial leaders play a significant role in influencing the creative employee engagement process. Recently, (Saeed et al., 2019) also found a significant and positive relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and the tendency of employees to be involved in the work process creatively (creative process engagement). Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Entrepreneurial leadership positively and significantly influences creative process engagement

The Influence of Creative Self-Efficacy on IWB

The basic concept of creative self-efficacy originates from self-efficacy theory; (Robbins et al., 2016) revealed that self-efficacy theory is also known as social cognitive theory or social learning theory, which refers to an individual's belief that he or she can do a particular job/task. Creative self-efficacy,

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as a form of employee self-confidence in producing creativity, shows a strong correlation with the high tendency of employees to behave innovatively in the workplace (Hsu et al., 2011). The results of recent research, for example, (Akbari et al., 2021; Teng et al., 2020), show that creative self-efficacy convincingly has a positive and significant effect on employee IWB. The findings of (Javed et al., 2020) also revealed similar results: creative self-efficacy is significantly related to employees' innovative work behavior. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Creative self-efficacy positively and significantly influences IWB

The Influence of Creative Process Engagement on IWB

(Saeed et al., 2019) explain that involvement in the creative process is a necessary first step towards innovation. Disturbed by advertisements, they will then avoid the advertisement (Nguyen & Khoa, 2019). Several other studies also presented similar results. (Kim & Park, 2017; Saeed et al., 2019; Uddin et al., 2020) explained that there is a positive and significant correlation between creative process engagement and employee IWB. These findings indicate that the higher the creative involvement process of employees, the higher their tendency to display IWB. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Creative process engagement has a positive and significant effect on IWB

The Influence of Creative Self-Efficacy in Mediating the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Leadership and IWB

Entrepreneurial leadership, characterized by Framing the challenge, Absorbing uncertainty, Path-clearing, Building commitment, and Specifying limits, can encourage employee confidence in generating creative ideas (Fatoki, 2021). Entrepreneurial leaders are likely to create creative self-efficacy in their employees because this leadership emphasizes creative and innovative thinking (Cai et al., 2019). Aside from playing a direct role in increasing IWB, creative self-efficacy has also been proven to mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and IWB. Mehmood et al. (2020) confirmed that entrepreneurial leaders, directly or indirectly, through creative self-efficacy, have a significant relationship with employee IWB. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Creative self-efficacy can mediate the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on IWB.

The Influence of Creative Process Engagement in Mediating the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Leadership and IWB

Saeed et al., (2019) explain that involvement in the creative process is a necessary first step towards innovation. Recent empirical studies show that creative process engagement strongly influences IWB (Afrin et al., 2022; Knezović & Drkić, 2021). Aside from directly influencing IWB, creative process engagement also plays a role in mediating the influence of entrepreneurial leaders on IWB (Khan, 2021; Saeed et al., 2019). Leadership style can influence a person's involvement in the creative process (M. T. et al., 2019), encouraging employees to display high IWB (Afrin et al., 2022). Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: Creative process engagement can mediate the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on IWB

Conceptual Framework of the Research

This research investigates four primary constructs: one independent variable (Entrepreneurial Leadership) and one dependent variable (Innovative Work Behavior). This research also added two mediating variables (Creative self-efficacy and Creative Process Engagement). For more details, see Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Research Framework and Hypothesis

3. Materials and Methods

Because there are specific criteria for selecting samples, a non-probability approach with a purposive sampling technique was used to determine samples for this research, and the models for this research were 150 Food and Beverage MSEs in Malang City. The data collection technique in this research uses a questionnaire distributed online and offline. The analysis method in this research uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) with the help of SmartPLS 3.0 software. All indicators used to measure the variables in this research were adopted from several previous studies. Indicators of the entrepreneurial leadership variable from Bagheri & (Caldwell et al., 2015; Soni N, Mehta S, Satpathy G, 2014) consist of 5 indicators. The creative self-efficacy variable is measured using three arrows referring to research (Karwowski, 2011). The Creative Process Engagement variable (Z2) is measured using three indicators adopted from research (Zhang, 2010); (Reiter-Palmon & Illies, 2004). The Innovative Work Behavior variable is measured using four indicators adopted from research (Javed, B., Khan & Quratulain, 2018)

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Results and Discussions

Results

Statistical tests were carried out to measure the validity and reliability of this research. Table 1 indicates that the scale, magnitude, and statistical suitability were acceptable. The average variance extracted (AVE) value of all latent variables shows a score of 0.655 for the Creative Self Efficacy variable, 0.642 for the Innovative Work Behavior variable, 0.594 for the Creative Process Engagement variable, and 0.585 for the Entrepreneurial Leadership variable. The Cronbach alpha value for the reliability criteria is relatively high; Entrepreneurial Leadership has the highest Cronbach alpha value. Sequentially, the Cronbach alpha coefficient values for the four variables used in this research ranged from 0.86 to 0.95, so all variables were acceptable.

Table 1. Composite Reliability, Cronbach Alpha, AVE

Variables	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha	AVE
Entrepreneurial Leadership	0.957	0.952	0.585
Creative Self Efficacy	0.930	0.912	0.655
Creative Process Engagement	0.898	0.863	0.594
Innovative Work Behavior	0.926	0.906	0.642

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023

The composite reliability (CR) values are 0.957, 0.930, 0.926, 0.898 (above 0.80), respectively. It can be concluded that all constructs are reliable, both according to composite reliability and Cronbach alpha. The R-square value of the Innovative Work Behavior variable in this research model is 0.877. Goodness of Fit (GoF) in this study was calculated using the equation $GoF = \sqrt{(0.67 \times 0.505)} = 0.58$. A score of 0.58 in the goodness of fit calculation shows that the model in this study can be said to have a large goodness of fit.

Table 2. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Relationship Between Variables	Path Coefficient	t-statistics	p-values	Results
H1	Entrepreneurial leadership → Innovative work behavior	0,271	2,736	0,006	Significant Accepted
H2	Entrepreneurial leadership → creative self-efficacy	0,739	14,345	0,000	Significant Accepted
H3	Entrepreneurial leadership → creative process engagement	0,797	14,827	0,000	Significant Accepted
H4	Creative self-efficacy → innovative work behavior	0,156	2,288	0,022	Significant Accepted
H5	Creative process engagement → innovative work	0,569	5,032	0,000	Significant Accepted

H6	behavior Entrepreneurial leadership → Creative self efficacy → innovative work behavior	0,115	2,268	0,023	Significant	Accepted
H7	behavior Entrepreneurial leadership → Creative self efficacy → innovative work behavior	0,453	5,478	0,000	Significant	Accepted

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023

Based on the results of the analysis in table 2, it is known that the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on innovative work behavior has a favorable path coefficient of 0.271, the t-statistic value of 2.736 is greater than the t-table value of 1.97, and the probability value of 0.006 is smaller than 0.05. Based on the results of these calculations, entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior, so H1 can be accepted. The influence of entrepreneurial leadership on creative self-efficacy has a favorable path coefficient of 0.739, the t-statistic value of 14.345 is greater than the t-table value of 1.97, and the probability value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. Based on the results of these calculations, entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and significant effect on creative self-efficacy so that H2 can be accepted. The influence of entrepreneurial leadership on creative process engagement has a favorable path coefficient of 0.797, the t-statistic value of 14.827 is greater than the t-table value of 1.97, and the probability value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. Based on the results of these calculations, entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and significant effect on creative process engagement so that H3 can be accepted. The influence of Creative Self Efficacy on Innovative Work Behavior has a favorable path coefficient of 0.156, a t-statistic value of 2.288, more significant than the t-table value of 1.97, and a probability value of 0.022, more diminutive than 0.05. Based on the results of these calculations, it can be concluded that Creative self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior, so H4 can be accepted.

The influence of Creative process engagement on Innovative Work Behavior has a favorable path coefficient of 0.569, the t-statistic value of 5.032 is greater than the t-table value of 1.97, and the probability value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. Based on the results of these calculations, it can be concluded that Creative Process Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior, so H5 can be accepted. The indirect influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior through Creative Self Efficacy has a favorable path coefficient of 0.115, the t-statistic value of 2.268 is greater than the t-table value of 1.98, and the probability value of 0.023 is smaller than 0.05. Based on the results of these calculations, it can be concluded that Creative Self-efficacy mediates the influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior. Therefore, H6 can be accepted. The indirect effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior through Creative Process Engagement has a favorable path coefficient of 0.453, the t-statistic value of 5.478 is greater than the t-table value of 1.98, and the probability value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. Based on the results of these calculations, it can be concluded that Creative Process Engagement mediates the influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior, and it can be supposed that H7 is accepted.

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Discussion

Entrepreneurial Leadership Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Innovative Work Behavior

Based on research findings, the research results show that entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior with a coefficient figure of 0.271 and a significance of 0.006 which is smaller than 0.271. This illustrates that entrepreneurial leadership has a significant influence in increasing innovative work behavior, with another illustration that the better Entrepreneurial leadership will increase innovative work behavior in small, micro, food and beverage businesses in Malang City. The results of this research support the Social Cognitive Theory of (Bandura, 1997) which explains a theory that emphasizes the idea that most human learning occurs in a social environment. This research supports the research of (Bagheri et al., 2020; Newman et al., 2018), revealed that entrepreneurial leadership plays a significant and positive role in innovative work behavior. The results of this research are relevant to (Akbari et al., 2021) research that entrepreneurial leadership significantly increases employee innovative work behavior in high-tech SMEs.

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Creative Self Efficacy

The research results show that entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and significant effect on creative self-efficacy with a coefficient of 0.739 and a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. The results of this research reveal that entrepreneurial leadership has a significant influence in increasing creative self-efficacy, the better the entrepreneurial leadership of food and beverage MSE entrepreneurs in the city of Malang, the greater the creative self-efficacy. The results of this research support the Social Cognitive Theory of (Bandura, 1962) which explains a theory that emphasizes the idea that most human learning occurs in a social environment. This research is in line with research by (Caiels et al., 2021; Fatoki, 2021; Sarwoko, 2020) which shows the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on creative self-efficacy. The results of this research are also in accordance with research by (Sarwoko, 2020).

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Creative Process Engagement

The research results show that entrepreneurial leadership has a positive and significant effect on creative process engagement with a coefficient of 0.797 and a significance value of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.005. The results of this research reveal that entrepreneurial leadership has a significant influence on increasing creative process engagement. The results of this research support the Social Cognitive Theory of (Bandura, 1962), which explains a theory that emphasizes the idea that most human learning occurs in a social environment. This research is in line with research by (Khan, 2021; M. T. et al., 2019; Saeed et al., 2019; Yulivan, 2021), which shows the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on creative process engagement.

The Influence of Creative Self-Efficacy on Innovative Work Behavior

The research results show that creative self-efficacy positively affects innovative work behavior with a coefficient of 0.156 and a significance of 0.022, which is smaller than 0.005. This research

reveals that the better the creative self-efficacy of food and beverage MSE entrepreneurs in Malang, the better the innovative work behavior will be. The basic concept of creative self-efficacy originates from self-efficacy theory; (Robbins & Judge, 2017) revealed that self-efficacy theory is also known as social cognitive theory or social learning theory, which refers to an individual's belief that they can do a particular job/task. The results of this study are by previous research from (Akbari et al., 2021; Javed et al., 2020; Teng et al., 2020) which also revealed similar results that creative self-efficacy is significantly positively related to employees' innovative work behavior. IWB among employees increases when they have high confidence in generating creative ideas (Newman et al., 2018). This study's results align with the results of research by (Hsu et al., 2011; Newman et al., 2018), who found that employees with high creative self-efficacy will also show high innovative work behavior.

The Influence of Creative Process Engagement on Innovative Work Behavior

The research results show that creative process engagement has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior with a coefficient of 0.569 and a significance of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. The better the creative process engagement, the better it will be. The results of this research support the Social Cognitive Theory of (Bandura, 1962), which explains a theory that emphasizes the idea that most human learning occurs in a social environment. (Kim & Park, 2017; Saeed et al., 2019; Uddin et al., 2020) stated that creative process engagement has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior.

Creative Self-efficacy Mediates the Influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership with Innovative Work Behavior

This research shows that Entrepreneurial Leadership significantly impacts Innovative Work Behavior. However, the mediating impact of creative self-efficacy is known to be partial mediation. Thus, creative self-efficacy can bridge the influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior. However, without creative self-efficacy, Entrepreneurial Leadership will still be able to increase Innovative Work Behavior. The coefficient result of the indirect influence of creative self-efficacy on innovative work behavior is in the positive direction of 0.115 with a significance of 0.023, below 0.05. The results of this research support the Social Cognitive Theory of (Bandura, 1962), which explains a theory that emphasizes the idea that most human learning occurs in a social environment. This research aligns with (Akbari et al., 2021; Mehmood et al., 2020; Newman et al., 2018) state that creative self-efficacy can mediate the influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior.

The Influence of Creative Process Engagement in Mediating the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Leadership and Innovative Work Behavior

This research shows a direct influence between entrepreneurial leadership and innovative work behavior, tested by including creative process engagement as mediation. The test results show an indirect effect between entrepreneurial leadership and innovative work behavior, mediated by creative process engagement. Creative process engagement in this research can act as partial mediation. This means that the independent variable, namely entrepreneurial leadership, can directly influence the dependent variable in this research, namely innovative work behavior, without going through or involving the mediator variable, namely Creative process engagement. The coefficient

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result of the indirect influence of creative process engagement on innovative work behavior is in the positive direction of 0.453 with a significance of 0.000, less than 0.05. The results of this research support the Social Cognitive Theory of (Bandura, 1962) which explains a theory that emphasizes the idea that most human learning occurs in a social environment. This research aligns with (Afrin et al., 2022; Khan, 2021; Knezović & Drkić, 2021; M. T. et al., 2019; Saeed et al., 2019) state that creative process engagement can mediate the influence of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior.

4. Conclusion

Entrepreneurial leadership has been proven to significantly influence innovative work behavior directly. Entrepreneurial leadership has been proven to be able to increase creative self-efficacy. Entrepreneurial leadership has been proven to improve creative process engagement. The creative self-efficacy variable has been proven to increase innovative work behavior. The creative process engagement variable has been proven to increase innovative work behavior. Creative self-efficacy has been proven to mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and innovative work behavior. Creative process engagement mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and innovative work behavior. Recommendations for Future Research, It is hoped that further research can add samples to industries other than small food and beverage businesses, for example, creative industries, fashion, agribusiness, furniture, etc, future research could add employee incentive variables as mediating variables, which have not been used in this research.

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